

1 **Supporting Information for *Liu et al.***

2 **Title:** Climate–Vegetation–Topography coupling drives the formation of
3 compound land degradation patterns on the north-eastern Qinghai-Tibet Plateau

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16 **Supporting tables and Materials**

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29 **Text:**

30 **Text S1. Spatiotemporal Evolution of LUCC**

31 The spatial distribution of LUCC types shows significant differences across
32 different time periods (Figure S2). The largest area of conversion occurs between
33 grassland and bare land (Figure S2-h), with conversions exceeding 570.00 km² in all
34 years except for 2019–2022. In most years, the area of bare land converting into
35 grassland is greater than that of grassland converting into bare land. Additionally,
36 forests and glaciers primarily convert to shrubs and bare land, respectively, while
37 agricultural land is mainly converted into grassland.

38 Specifically, grassland, the predominant land type, is distributed in a strip-like
39 form along the Qilian Mountains from the summit of Daxue Mountain to the end of
40 the Lenglongling Mountain, covering more than half of the area, with its proportion
41 reaching 62.16% in 2019 (Figure S2-f). Bare land, with a proportion just below that of
42 grassland, is mainly distributed in blocks in the Daxue Mountain area, occupying
43 about one-third of the total area, with the largest proportion (34.69%) observed in
44 1997 (Figure S2-c). Forests and glaciers, in comparison to grassland and bare land,
45 account for less than 5.00% of the area and are mainly distributed sporadically in
46 block form in the Lenglongling Mountain and Danghe South Mountain areas. Shrubs,
47 water bodies, and agricultural land are primarily distributed as point features
48 throughout the study area, with each covering less than 1.00% of the total area.

49 **Figure:**

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51 **Figure S1. Geographical location of the study area.** Panel a, b, and c represent,
 52 respectively, the location of the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau and Qilian Mountain National Park in
 53 China, the LUC types of Qilian Mountain National Park on the northeastern edge of the Qinghai-
 54 Tibet Plateau, and the elevation distribution of Qilian Mountain National Park.

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56 **Figure S2. Distribution and Evolution Patterns of LUC Types.** Panels a-g
 57 represents the spatial distribution and area proportions of LUC at typical time points (1990, 1995,

58 1997, 2004, 2008, 2019, and 2022); panel h shows the conversion changes between different
 59 LUCC types in typical years.

60
 61 **Figure S3. Response of Different LUCC to Degradation Processes.** Panels a–h, i–p,
 62 and q–x represents the unit area erosion amounts and the area proportions of total erosion for
 63 different LUCC types at typical time points and over the past 33 years for SW, SD, and RD.

64

65 **Figure S4. Migration Characteristics of Degradation Intensity Levels in Different Time Periods.** Panels a–g, h–n, and o–u represent the

66 conversion changes between different erosion intensity levels of SW, SD, and RD in different time periods.

67

68 **Figure S5. Interrelationships Among Different Land Degradation Types.** The rows
 69 and columns represent different land degradation types, with the diagonal showing the distribution
 70 of each variable. The lower left corner corresponds to the scatter plots of the respective variables,
 71 which mainly represent the distribution characteristics between different variables. If the scatter
 72 plot distribution is concentrated and linear, it indicates a strong significant correlation between the
 73 variables; conversely, a more dispersed distribution suggests a weak correlation. For example, the
 74 scatter plot of SW and RD shows a relatively concentrated linear distribution, indicating a strong
 75 significant positive correlation between them. Asterisks (*) represent the significance level of
 76 correlation: *** indicates $P < 0.001$, ** indicates $P < 0.05$, and * indicates $P < 0.01$.

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78 **Figure S6. Integrated research framework and key findings on land degradation.**

79 Panel represent the study area, located on the northeastern edge of the Qinghai–Tibet Plateau, is
80 currently experiencing severe land degradation. This figure presents a comprehensive framework
81 composed of three parts: **(01)** Identification and assessment of land degradation, including
82 spatiotemporal evolution quantification, spatial migration trend analysis, and sensitivity evaluation;
83 **(02)** Mechanism exploration using Random Forest (RF) for variable importance identification,
84 LASSO for dimensionality reduction, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-
85 SEM) for causal pathway identification, and Spearman correlation for interaction analysis among
86 degradation types; **(03)** Key findings highlight that SW, SD, and RD show distinct spatial
87 heterogeneity, driven by different factors (vegetation–topography–climate–soil), with notable
88 interactions among them. The study emphasizes that climate–vegetation–topography coupling
89 shapes compound degradation patterns and underscores the importance of ecological restoration,
90 vegetation recovery, and sustainable land use in fragile alpine ecosystems.

91 **Table:**

92 **Table S1. Data Sources and Detailed Information**

Data Type	Data Source	Resolution
Climate environment (Precipitation, Temperature, Potential Evapotranspiration, and Aridity Index)	National Earth System Science Data Center Sharing Service Platform (http://www.geodata.cn)	1 km
LUCC	Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences (https://www.resdc.cn)	1 km
NDVI	National Scientific and Technological Resources Sharing Network (https://nesdc.org.cn/)	1 km
Soil	Based on the World Soil Database (HWSD) (https://poles.tpdc.ac.cn)	1 km
Topography (elevation, Slope, and Aspect)	Chinese Academy of Sciences Geospatial Data Cloud Platform (https://www.gscloud.cn)	30 m
Rainfall Erosivity (R)	Based on Precipitation Data	1 km
LS Slope Length and Steepness (LS)	Based on DEM Data	1 km
Vegetation Factor (C)	Based on NDVI Data	1 km
Soil Texture		1 km
Carbonate Content	Based on the World Soil Database (HWSD) (https://poles.tpdc.ac.cn)	1 km
Human Footprint Index	(https://www.x-mol.com)	1 km
Population Density	https://landscan.ornl.gov/	1 km
GDP	Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences (https://www.resdc.cn)	1 km

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